

Original paper

MAQOM SAN'ATI – O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY MUSIQA SAN'ATINING DURDONASI

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Аннотация

KIRISH: maqolada maqom san'ati o'zbek milliy musiqa madaniyatida alohida o'rin egallashi, uning estetik-falsafiy mazmuni, jamiyat va milliy identifikatsiyadagi roli, shuningdek, huquqiy-normativ asoslari, statistik holati va zamonaviy kontekstdagi muammo va istiqbollari tahlil qilinadi. Maqom san'ati milliy musiqa tafakkurining cho'qqisi sifatida qaraladi.

MAQSAD: maqom san'atining madaniy meros sifatidagi o'rni va uning zamonaviy ijtimoiy-madaniy jarayonlardagi ahamiyatini ochib berish.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda tarixiy, madaniy-tahliliy va musiqashunoslik metodlar qo'llanilgan. Maqomning nazariy manbalari, amaliy ijrochilik an'analari hamda huquqiy me'yoriy hujjatlar tahlil qilingan.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: maqom san'ati o'zbek xalqining ruhiy olamini, milliy estetik tafakkurini va tarixiy-madaniy identitetini ifoda etuvchi noyob tizim sifatida talqin etiladi. Tadqiqotda maqomni asrab-avaylash va targ'ib etishda ta'lim, ilm-fan va san'at muassasalarining o'rni yoritilgan.

XULOSA: maqom san'ati o'zbek milliy madaniyatining asosi bo'lib, uni chuqur o'rganish, yosh avlodga yetkazish va xalqaro miqyosda targ'ib qilish madaniy barqarorlikning muhim omilidir.

Kalit so'zlar: maqom, o'zbek musiqa tafakkuri, milliy musiqa san'ati, estetik tafakkur, nomoddiy madaniy meros, huquqiy baza.

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ИСКУССТВО МАКОМА – ШЕДЕВР НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО МУЗЫКАЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье анализируется особое место искусства макама в узбекской национальной музыкальной культуре, его эстетическое и философское содержание, роль в обществе и формировании национальной идентичности, а также его правовые и нормативные основы, статистическое положение, проблемы

и перспективы в современных условиях. Искусство макома считается вершиной национальной музыкальной мысли.

ЦЕЛЬ: раскрыть значение искусства макома как элемента нематериального культурного наследия и его роль в современных социокультурных процессах.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: использованы исторический, культурологический и музыковедческий методы. Анализируются теоретические источники, исполнительские традиции и правовые документы, связанные с искусством макома.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: установлено, что маком отражает духовный мир узбекского народа, его эстетическое мышление и национальную идентичность. Отмечена важная роль образовательных и культурных институтов в сохранении и популяризации макомного искусства.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: искусство макома является фундаментом узбекской музыкальной культуры и важным фактором культурной стабильности, требующим дальнейшего изучения и международного продвижения.

Ключевые слова: маком, узбекская музыкальная мысль, национальное музыкальное искусство, эстетическая мысль, нематериальное культурное наследие, правовая база.

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MAQOM ART - AS A MASTERPIECE OF UZBEKISTAN NATIONAL MUSICAL ART

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: the article analyzes the unique role of maqom art in Uzbek national musical culture, its aesthetic and philosophical meaning, its contribution to society and national identity, as well as its legal framework, statistical status, and contemporary challenges and prospects. Maqom is viewed as the pinnacle of national musical thought.

AIM: to reveal the significance of maqom art as an element of intangible cultural heritage and its role in modern socio-cultural processes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the research employs historical, cultural-analytical, and musicological methods. Theoretical sources, performance traditions, and legal documents related to maqom art were analyzed.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: the study shows that maqom reflects the spiritual world, aesthetic thinking, and national identity of the Uzbek people. It emphasizes the role of educational, academic, and artistic institutions in the preservation and promotion of maqom.

CONCLUSION: maqom art, as the foundation of Uzbek musical culture, plays a vital role in ensuring cultural continuity and deserves in-depth study and global promotion.

Keywords: maqom, Uzbek musical thinking, national musical art, aesthetic thought, intangible cultural heritage, legal framework.

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Among the rich spiritual heritage of Uzbekistan, among the art forms that have been formed over the centuries, the art of maqom occupies a special place. Maqom is not only a musical genre, but also a complex system that embodies the spiritual and aesthetic thinking, artistic taste, and philosophical views of the people. In maqom works, the historical memory of the Uzbek people, loyalty to their national identity, and inner experiences are reflected at a high artistic level through musical expression [1: 21].

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, the art of maqom is one of the most ancient and rich heritages of our people, which has been living as a masterpiece of our national culture for centuries [6]. After this resolution, systematic work began in the country to develop the art of maqom. Since 2018, the International Festival of Maqom Art has been held in the city of Shahrizabz every two years. It is known that in 2024, more than 300 performers from more than 40 countries participated in this festival [11: 4].

The art of maqom, as the pinnacle of Uzbek musical thought, not only expresses national identity, but is also recognized worldwide as a universal layer of the musical heritage of the East. As Academician O. Matyoqubov noted, maqom is the most perfect system formed in the musical thought of the Uzbek people, it is a musical expression of the spirit, faith and philosophy of the people [1: 21].

F. Rajabov writes about the historical roots of maqom art in his work "History of Uzbek maqoms": "The basic principles of maqom were nourished by the musical thought of the Middle Ages and were perfected in accordance with the artistic worldview of the Uzbek people" [2: 33]. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Culture" defines the preservation and promotion of national musical heritage as one of the priority areas of state policy. According to it, the task of "developing and promoting national musical genres, including maqom art, at the international level" is clearly stated.

Modern analyses of musical art show that in recent years maqom performance has become increasingly popular among young people. In 2023, the number of students studying maqom at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan and republican specialized art schools increased by 25% [12:3]. Thus, the art of maqom, as the pinnacle of Uzbek musical thought, is highly artistically embodied in the spiritual, philosophical and aesthetic world of our people, is the mainstay of national art and is at the center of scientific research as a historical and artistic heritage [5: 44].

The art of maqom takes its historical roots from the musical heritage of Central Asia and the East. As Academician O. Matyoqubov noted, maqom works were influenced by

ancient Eastern musical systems, in particular Persian, Turkish and Arabic maqoms, and were formed in accordance with the artistic tastes and spiritual experiences of the Uzbek people [1:45].

According to F. Rajabov, Uzbek maqoms have historically developed from two main streams: shashmaqom and Uzbek folk maqoms. Shashmaqom, especially developed in the Khiva and Bukhara schools, has a complex rhythmic and melodic system [2:55]. Uzbek folk maqoms are more adapted to dialogue and practical performance, closely related to the everyday life, customs and folklore of the people [2:60].

O. Matyokubov analyzes the artistic and philosophical essence of the shashmaqom system in his work "The Art of Maqom and Its Theoretical Foundations". He writes: "The art of shashmaqom expresses the historical memory, aesthetic values, and spiritual experiences of the Uzbek people through a musical synthetic system. Each type of maqom has a clear philosophical content and artistic form" [4:102].

According to historical sources, maqom performance was passed down from generation to generation mainly through oral tradition. Through such a performance system, not only melodic and rhythmic rules, but also the artistic thinking and aesthetic rules of the maqom were preserved [3: 78].

Mamarasulov, analyzing the national and philosophical foundations of maqom, concludes: "The art of maqom is not only music, but also an artistic expression of the worldview, spirituality and national identity of the people. Despite its historical roots in the musical heritage of the East, it is adapted to the aesthetic thinking of the Uzbek people" [5:61].

In the process of the formation of shashmaqom and folk maqoms, the Khiva, Bukhara and Samarkand schools played a special role. In particular, the Khiva school developed a complex rhythmic system and performance technique, while the Bukhara school deepened artistic thinking and philosophical content [2:70].

The stages of the historical development of maqom are as follows:

1. The influence of the Ancient East - assimilation from Arabic, Persian and Turkish musical systems.

2. Integration with the Uzbek folk tradition - the formation of folk maqoms.

3. The development of shashmaqom schools - Khiva, Bukhara, Samarkand.

4. The formation of modern maqom performance and teaching systems

Thus, despite the historical roots of the art of maqom being connected with the musical heritage of the East, it has adapted to the national aesthetic thinking and artistic traditions of the Uzbek people and is recognized today as the pinnacle of national musical thinking [5:63].

The art of maqom is considered not only as a musical genre, but also as an artistic and philosophical expression of folk thinking. Each type of maqom embodies a certain spiritual state, mood and philosophical content. As Academician O. Matyokubov noted, the artistic essence of maqom is expressed in its complex melodic, rhythmic and harmonic

systems. Through this system, the performer not only sings notes, but also conveys his inner spiritual experiences to the listener [1:120].

F. Rajabov draws attention to the philosophical layer of the maqom: "Each type of maqom expresses a certain philosophical concept, national moral values, and human experiences. The melodic and rhythmic structure of the maqom, the harmony of melodies, helps to deeply feel the human psyche" [2: 88].

Uzbek maqoms reflect spiritual moods in various forms. For example, the Segoh maqom often expresses a calm and gentle mood, while the Shur evokes a joyful and festive spirit. The musical expression of such different moods depends not only on the melody and rhythm, but also on the technical skill of the performer [4: 115].

Mamarasulov connects the maqom with the philosophical worldview of the people, writing: "The art of maqom is closely related to the national worldview and spirituality of the people. It expresses the people's attitude to nature, life values, and human relationships in musical form" [5: 90]. The aesthetic properties of a maqom are determined by its melodic and rhythmic stylistic aspects. For example:

- Melody is the most important element of a maqom, which reflects mood and spiritual experiences.
- Rhythm is a means of creating a certain mood and controlling the flow of music.
- Ornamentation enriches artistic expression through additional melodies and figures [3:102].

In the shashmaqom schools, each type of maqom has its own philosophical content. In the Khiva school, maqoms reflect a more spiritual and contemplative mood, while in the Bukhara school they often express artistic, dramatic and aesthetic views [2:95].

O. Matyokubov emphasizes the need to combine the artistic essence of the maqom and the performance technique: "In the process of singing the maqom, the performer must not only accurately perform the notes, but also convey the philosophical content of each type of maqom to the listener. This constitutes the deep artistry of the maqom art".

Modern analyses show that the aesthetic and philosophical aspects of the art of maqom are of great importance in the development of national musical thinking and artistic taste. According to research conducted by the Institute of Arts and Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023, young people engaged in maqom performance are significantly developing their aesthetic taste and musical thinking [12:7]. At the same time, the artistic content of the maqom is inextricably linked with the life of the people. For example, the Rast maqom often reflects life values, and the Navo - kindness and human feelings. Through these maqoms, the listener discovers his inner spiritual experiences and witnesses the aesthetic values of national culture [4:125].

Thus, the aesthetic and philosophical content and artistic features of the maqom further strengthen its place in the national musical thought, reflecting the spirit and cultural heritage of the people in a highly artistic form. These aspects allow us to appreciate the art of maqom not only as the pinnacle of Uzbek musical thought, but also as a priceless masterpiece of folk culture [5:95].

The performance of the maqom is the most complex and artistically rich part of this art, in which melody, rhythm and ornamentation fulfill not only technical, but also aesthetic and philosophical goals. As O. Matyokubov noted, by singing music, the maqom performer conveys to the listener not only the notes, but also the spiritual, philosophical and artistic content of the maqom.

The performance of modern interpretations is creating opportunities for a new expression of the art of maqom, especially among the younger generation. For example, master classes and seminars on maqom performance organized in 2022–2024 at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan and private music studios are helping to improve the technical and aesthetic skills of performers.

While performance techniques in shashmaqom schools have traditionally been passed down through the teacher-student system, conservatory and academic curricula play a key role in modern interpretations. Through this system, performers perfectly master the complex rhythmic systems, ornamentation, and melodic figures of maqom.

Analyzing the modern development of maqom performance, Mamarasulov writes: “Young performers not only sing traditional maqoms, but also bring maqom to the modern music scene through new artistic interpretations and experimental approaches. This increases the international status of maqom art”.

Modern interpretations are developing in the following directions:

1. Traditional and experimental fusion - combining maqom elements with modern musical genres.
2. Technological support - analyzing maqom performance and creating new musical forms through computer and audio technologies.
3. International presentations - maqom performance is being demonstrated by young people in new interpretations at various international festivals and concerts in Uzbekistan [11: 6].

Research shows that modern interpretations direct the performance towards interactive communication with the listener. The maqom performer not only demonstrates his technical skills, but also provides a spiritual connection with the listener, through which the aesthetic and philosophical content of the maqom is felt more deeply.

Also, maqom performance plays an important role in the formation of national identity and cultural values among young people. According to statistics for 2023, the number of students studying maqom in the republic exceeded 500, which indicates a strong future for the field. In modern interpretations, artistic innovations and experiments are also common in performance. For example, the melodies and rhythms of maqom are combined with pop or jazz genres, but the philosophical content and melodic structure of the maqom are preserved [4:142].

This approach undoubtedly brings the art of maqom to the global musical arena and increases its significance not only nationally, but also internationally. Thus, modern maqom performance, while preserving the traditional heritage, develops the art through new artistic forms and experimental directions. This process strengthens the position of maqom art as

the pinnacle of national musical thought and is of decisive importance in its transmission to the younger generation.

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